

Differences in ratooning ability among rice cultivars

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We screened 24 rice hybrids, varieties, and breeding lines for ratoon tillers/hill and ratoon tillers/node 10 d after cutting at the first (top) node.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Plants were transplanted at 16.7- × 23.3-cm spacing at 2 seedlings/hill.

Most of the hybrids had good ratooning ability (see table). Hunanzaishengdao, Dyou 10, and Minghui 63 grew tillers from all nodes. Jiang 86-419 and Shanyou 66 formed tillers mainly from the lower nodes. Aiyou 1 developed tillers mainly from the higher nodes. Jiang 86-697 and Jiang 86-315 regenerated tillers mainly from mid-nodes. □

Average numbers of ratoon tillers on different nodes in 24 rice hybrids, varieties, and breeding lines.^a Zigang, Sichuan, China, 1987.

Variety	Ratoon tillers/hill	Ratoon tillers/node ^b			
		2	3	4	5
Dyou 10 ^c	30.1 a	6.5 ab	7.9 a	10.3 a	5.3 c
Shanyou 66 ^c	29.5 a	1.3 c	4.5 b	10.3 a	13.3 a
Minghui 63 ^c	29.1 a	6.7 ab	8.1 a	7.9 bc	6.5 bc
Dyou 63 ^c	26.7 ab	2.9 bc	6.2 ab	9.5 ab	8.1 bc
Shanyou 63 ^c	25.9 ab	3.9 bc	7.1 ab	9.4 ab	5.5 c
Feigai 63 ^c	25.6 ab	7.0 ab	8.2 a	8.7 ab	1.7 d
40-1	25.2 ab	5.7 ab	5.3 b	7.1 bc	7.1 bc
Jiang 86-842	25.1 ab	7.4 a	7.2 ab	7.4 bc	3.1 cd
Xieyou 63 ^c	25.1 ab	4.5 ab	6.3 ab	8.4 b	5.8 bc
Aiyou 1 ^c	22.9 b	3.7 bc	6.9 ab	4.4 d	2.5 cd
Jiang 86-808	21.8 bc	2.0 c	5.3 b	7.7 bc	7.0 bc
Jiang 86-419	21.5 bc	0.0 c	2.0 c	8.5 ab	10.9 ab
Jiang 86-357	19.8 bc	0.4 c	3.5 bc	7.1 bc	8.7 b
Hunanzaishengdao	19.1 bc	5.0 b	3.9 bc	5.7 cd	4.5 cd
85-3304	17.6 c	4.8 b	6.3 ab	5.6 cd	0.9 d
Gangai 63 ^c	17.5 c	3.7 bc	6.9 ab	4.4 d	2.5 cd
86-6052	17.1 c	0.7 c	6.9 ab	6.3 c	3.1 cd
Jiang 86-313	17.0 c	0.3 c	6.4 ab	5.7 cd	4.8 cd
86-6046	16.9 c	1.9 c	7.3 ab	5.8 cd	1.9 d
Jiang 86-315	16.5 c	1.1 c	7.7 a	6.3 c	1.5 d
86-6058	15.6 c	1.3 c	5.9 ab	6.1 cd	3.1 cd
Jiang 86-334	15.1 c	2.1 c	7.2 ab	5.1 cd	0.7 d
Jiang 86-697	14.7 c	0.9 c	5.9 ab	6.5 c	1.4 d
Jiang 86-333	14.6 c	0.7 c	6.5 ab	6.1 cd	1.3 d

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b2, 3, 4, 5 indicate node number counting from top to bottom. ^cHybrids.

Grain quality

Physicochemical characters of some rice cultivars of West Bengal

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The grain quality characters of 15 popularly cultivated rice varieties of West Bengal grown in 1986 wet season were evaluated after grain storage under ambient condition.

Length was 5.45-7.14 mm and length/breadth ratio was 3.47-2.31 (see table). The alkali spreading value ranged between 7 (CN776-U6-B2-II) and 3 (IET4786).

Physicochemical characters of some rice cultivars. West Bengal, India, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Endosperm chalkiness ^a	Brown rice			L/B ratio	1000-grain wt (g)	Milled rice				
		Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	Thickness (mm)			Alkali spreading value	Amylose (%)	Elongation ratio	Volume expansion ratio	Water uptake (ml/100 g of rice)
IR42	3	6.78	2.20	1.58	3.08	16.3	6.0	24.5	1.44	3.81	200.0
IET2254	1	6.36	2.09	1.64	3.04	15.5	4.8	18.6	1.52	4.73	222.5
IET4094	0	7.14	2.06	1.60	3.47	15.3	5.0	34.7	1.73	4.71	218.5
IET4786	0	5.66	1.64	1.56	3.38	12.8	3.0	19.5	1.64	4.00	212.5
CN776-U6-B2-II	5	7.03	2.12	1.75	3.33	18.2	7.0	20.5	1.50	4.67	222.5
IET1444	0	5.94	2.29	1.88	2.59	15.8	5.5	25.6	1.56	5.39	288.0
Jaya	7	6.51	2.39	1.83	2.72	20.7	7.0	31.1	1.44	4.93	287.5
CR237-1	1	6.87	1.95	1.73	3.52	16.4	4.0	29.4	1.22	4.47	252.5
IET2815	0	7.14	2.06	1.70	3.08	16.9	5.6	28.8	1.47	4.50	250.0
IR30	3	5.45	2.23	1.79	2.44	15.9	6.2	25.9	1.61	4.73	221.5
IR20	0	6.71	2.03	1.69	3.30	16.5	5.0	25.3	1.54	4.83	220.0
CN747-8-1	0	6.72	1.90	1.64	2.54	16.1	5.0	27.2	1.70	5.45	252.5
IET6141	1	6.36	1.90	1.61	3.38	16.0	5.2	34.5	1.62	4.72	237.5
IR36	1	6.78	2.08	1.66	3.26	16.7	4.0	26.3	1.74	5.26	262.5
CSR4	7	5.53	2.39	1.64	2.31	14.2	4.1	29.1	1.72	5.04	175.0

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.